

FREE AND INFORMED CONSENT FORM - ICF

You are being invited to participate, as a volunteer, in the research entitled **XXXXXXXXXXXX**. My name is **XXXXXXXXXXXX**, I am the principal investigator and my area of expertise is **XXXXXXXXXXXX**. After receiving the following clarifications and information, if you agree to participate in the study, please sign at the end of this document, which is printed in duplicate, one copy for you and the other for me. I clarify that in case of refusal to participate, at any stage of the research, you will not be penalized in any way. However, if you agree to participate, any questions about the research can be clarified by the principal investigator via email **XXXXXXXXXXXX** and through the following telephone contact: **XXXXXXXXXXXX**, including the possibility of a collect call. If you still have questions about your rights as a participant in this research, you can also contact the Research Ethics Committee of **XXXXXXXXXXXX**, by telephone **XXXXXXXXXXXX**, which is the body responsible for resolving doubts related to the ethical nature of the research. The Research Ethics Committee of **XXXXXXXXXXXX** is an independent, public body with an advisory, educational, and deliberative character, created to protect the well-being of research participants, their integrity and dignity, and to contribute to the development of research within current ethical standards.

The general objective of this research is to evaluate a Catalog of Privacy Requirements Standards (CPRP), developed to assist in specifying requirements in accordance with the General Data Protection Law (LGPD). You will be invited to answer two questionnaires: one to provide information about your professional profile and experience with related topics, and another to provide information about your perception of participating in the activities of this research. You are entitled to reimbursement of expenses arising from cooperation with the research, including transportation and meals, if applicable. In case of damages, you have the right to claim compensation, as provided by law.

If you do not wish your name to be disclosed, confidentiality is guaranteed to ensure privacy and anonymity. The information from this research will be confidential and will only be disclosed at scientific events or publications. The risks of participating in this research are: stress, mental fatigue, dissatisfaction, and emotional risks when developing the activities proposed in this research. Participants will be monitored throughout the development of this research to minimize risks and harm. Researchers and supervising professors will be in contact with participants to monitor the occurrence of possible risks and, if they occur, referral to a mental health professional will be made, and if necessary, the participant may request the suspension of their consent. The benefits of this research include the experience gained using a CPRP to assist in specifying requirements in accordance with the LGPD (Brazilian General Data Protection Law).

The mechanisms for sending confidential study information are subject to strict control and privacy procedures, governed by the General Data Protection Law (Law N°. 13.709/2018), undergoing an anonymization process in order to protect the participant's identity and the data collected by the study. Throughout the research period and in the dissemination of results, your privacy will be respected; that is, your name or any other data or element that could, in any way, identify you, will be kept confidential. All material will be kept in my custody for a minimum period of five years.

At the end of the research, after the analyses have been carried out, the research results will be shared with the participating students via the email provided in the profile questionnaire, and through the publication of scientific articles.

To conduct data collection, your consent is required. Please initial the option in parentheses that validates your decision:

- I allow the collection of my data for research purposes.
- I do not allow my data to be collected for research purposes.

We may also need to use your opinion in publications. Please initial the option in parentheses that validates your decision:

- I allow the disclosure of my opinion in the published results of the research.
- I do not allow my opinion to be included in the published research results.

There may also be a need to use your image in publications. Please initial the option in parentheses that validates your decision:

- I authorize the use of my image in the published research results.
- I do not allow my image to be used in the published research results.

The data collected may need to be used in future research, provided that a new evaluation is carried out by XXXXX. Please authorize this, validating your decision with a checkmark in the parentheses below:

- I acknowledge that the data collected from me may be relevant to future research and therefore authorize the storage of this material in a database.
- I acknowledge that the data collected from me may be relevant to future research, but I do not authorize the storage of this material in a database.

For any questions, suggestions, or problems, you can contact the researchers or those in charge at XXXXXXXXXXXX. The contact phone numbers are: XXXXXXXXXXXX.

1.2 Consent to Participate as a Research Participant:

I,, the undersigned, agree to participate in the study entitled XXXXXXXXXXXX. I state that I am ____ years old and emphasize that my participation in this research is voluntary. I have been duly informed by the responsible researcher XXXXXXXXXXXX about the research, the procedures and methods involved, as well as the possible risks and benefits arising from my participation in the study. I have been assured that I can withdraw my consent at any time without incurring any penalty. I therefore declare that I agree to participate in the research project described above.

- The participant confirms that they have received the information, are over 18 years of age, and agree to participate in the research.

XXXXXX, from from

Full signature of the participant

Full signatures of witnesses

Full signature of the responsible researcher.